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**WORD-OF-MOUTH COMMUNICATION AND ITS IMPACT ON BUYING
REPLACEMENT TYRES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
COMMERCIAL VEHICLES IN TAMILNADU**

*Dr. K. NATARAJAN * & Dr. K. SOUNDARARAJAN ***

Introduction

The major change in the market that should be mentioned first is the ever increasing supply of communication channels. There was a fairly manageable number of media in the 1960s (TV, radio, magazine, newspaper), but by the end of the 1990s the Internet and mobile communications had become two further media competing for the attention of the consumer. In addition, for years there has been an increasing fragmentation within the various communication channels (Rosen, 2009).

Since consumers media addiction has not kept pace with this rise, the perception of communication and advertising messages within the individual channels has decreased dramatically. This development is also fostered by the fact that advertising messages are sent through communication channels that are now used by the corresponding target audiences to only a reduced extent. Now a day's advertising companies still use television as central medium of communication, whereas consumers – particularly the most sought-after target group increasingly use the Internet. As a result, companies are faced by steadily growing mainstream media pressure, which frequently ends in consumers being inundated by a plethora of advertising. WOM is mischievously nicknamed free advertising. If advertising can be defined as 'any paid form of non personal presentation of ideas, goods or services by an identified sponsor' (Alexander, 1964), then most WOM is not. Advertising, by this definition, is paid, nonpersonal, transparently sponsored communication. These distinguishing characteristics of WOM are being eroded. Some WOM is incentivized and rewarded, while other WOM is produced electronically. Perhaps all that distinguishes WOM is that it is uttered by sources that are assumed by receivers to be independent of corporate influence. WOM can be characterized by valence, focus, timing, solicitation and intervention. Firms in many industries release or distribute their new products, often those that have shorter lifecycles, in a sequence of stages. It is often their practice as well to launch separate advertising campaigns at each distribution stage. In this context, promotion mix ele-

ments, advertising and Word-of-Mouth (WOM), can play important, separate, and yet interdependent roles in stimulating demand, often with the effectiveness of both elements varying within and across distribution stages. Before expecting to benefit from WOM around any new product, it is also essential to know the degree to which consumers actually use WOM as a basis for their purchase decisions. For randomly selected brands that they now use, participants in the survey were asked to think about a recent replacement purchase for their commercial vehicles tyre. Which of these, they were asked, were influential in terms of which brand they bought or seriously considered?, Things they heard from other people including conversations, but also what they read in e- mail, blogs, etc. Seeing other people using the brands or considering, Advertisement which they read in magazines, newspapers, or websites. Considering these factors we can understand Consumers often talk about the products and services they use, and are influenced in their choices by the opinions of others. Categories differ widely in influence of WOM. Just because consumers frequently share opinions about a brand assure that WOM will also be highly influential. Generally Low-priced packaged goods tend not to depend on WOM. Some combination of high price, risk and entertainment value often-but not always-distinguishes categories where WOM is most potent.

Word-of-mouth (WOM) and Word-of-mouth Marketing (WOMM)

Defining word of mouth (WOM) precisely, however, has proven difficult (Carl, 2006; Nyi-

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Arndt (1967) defines it as 'face-to-face communication about a brand, product or service between people who are perceived as not having connections to a commercial entity'. The American Word of Mouth Marketing Association (WOMMA), founded in 2005, defined word of mouth (WOM) very generally as 'the act of consumers providing information to other consumers' (WOMMA, 2008). Both definitions conceive of word of mouth (WOM) as natural (that is, noncommercial), interpersonal communication about brands, products or services that may be either positive or negative (WOMMA, 2008). In this sense, word of mouth marketing (WOMM) is seen as the type of marketing that specifically promotes natural interpersonal communication in the most diverse ways. It describes it as: 'Giving people a reason to talk about your products and services, and making it easier for that conversation to take place. It is the art and science of building active, mutually beneficial consumer-to-consumer and consumer-to-marketer communications'. In this definition, word-of-mouth marketing becomes a generic term, including tactics such as so-called 'viral marketing' or 'buzz marketing' (Sernovitz, 2007). Word-of-mouth marketing is accordingly not about generating conversations between consumers, but rather to encourage these conversations and to anchor them in the overall marketing strategy (Sernovitz, 2007). The focus on overall marketing is important because the theory of communication practice often speaks of marketing when it means only marketing communication and not the entire marketing mix (with product, price and place) (Kotler, 2006).

Importance of word of mouth in business and consumer perspectives

Already in the late 1970s the growing importance of word of mouth in the realization of purchasing processes was empirically confirmed again and again. Thus, for example, for 67 per cent of the respondents in a study carried out by GfK Roper Consulting, recommendations from the social environment were the most important source of information, far ahead of TV-spots and print media, which

were mentioned as a source of information by only 53 per cent and 47 per cent respectively (GfK Roper Consulting, 2006). Within the last thirty years the importance of word of mouth has increased substantially once again. According to an internet-based survey 'Trust, Value and Engagement in Advertising', repeatedly carried out by the market research institution Nielsen for the first time in 2007 and then in 2009, over 25,000 Internet users surveyed from 50 countries primarily trust in the recommendations of other consumers (90 per cent) and in consumer opinions published online (70 per cent). Traditional media such as newspapers (61 per cent), television (61 per cent) and radio (55 per cent) are mentioned, but they trail significantly behind interpersonal communication (The Nielsen Company, 2009). This study provides norms or benchmarks for the incidence, influence and overall potency of WOM in a variety of consumer categories. Planning for brands in these categories needs to recognize both the potential and limitations that go with those categories.

Statement of the Problem

Commercial Vehicles (CVs) segment covers buses and trucks classified as Medium and Heavy Commercial Vehicles (M & HCVs) and Van, station wagons and smaller weight vehicles, characterized a Light Commercial Vehicles (LCVs). The demand of tyres flows from three segments – Original Equipment (OE), Replacements and Exports. Of the three, the replacement market is the primary source of demand, followed by the OE segment and exports. The study's problem can be formulated according to the following statement: "Word of mouth plays an important role in the buying decision in the Replacement Tyre buyer." And the discussion of this problem will be according to the following objectives.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To study the major sources of information for purchasing the Replacement tyre.

- To identify the source which is more influential?
- Defining the role of word-of-mouth as one of marketing tools.

Area of Research and Sampling Procedure

The study aims at analyzing how various sources of information influence the consumers in replacement of tyres in commercial vehicles segments. Tamilnadu state consists of 32 districts. These districts are grouped under 11 regional transport areas. Transport Regions offices are classified by the state transport authority, Government of Tamilnadu. Hence, after analyzing the available data, the researcher has chosen these zones that are the most suited to collect data. Here, the researcher has adopted multistage stage random sampling technique. These zones are classified into two categories namely the highest and the lowest numbers of vehicles that are registered. One zone from each category has been selected for the present study. At the second stage, two blocks from each zone have been chosen for the study, one block represents the highest number of vehicles registered and the other block represents lowest number of vehicles registered. In the third stage, in each block 125 owners are conveniently selected for the study. Hence, totally 485 consumers are considered for the present study. The selection of study area is based on multi stage random sampling technique. But, the selections of sample respondents are based on convenient sampling technique. Convenient sampling procedure is used to obtain those owners most conveniently available.

Collection of the Primary Data

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a structured questionnaire administered in person from the consumer regarding their opinion about their satisfaction on the product, The respondents of this study are owners of the Light and Heavy commercial vehicles who have replaced their product after using the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) in

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Coimbatore, Chennai, Thanjavure, and Virudhunagar zones. The respondents were approached to collect information. The researcher has totally collected 485 responses and found fit for further analysis.

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Collection of the Secondary Data

The researcher collected secondary data on sales trends, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the replacement action. This information has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

Statistical Tools Used

Responses are coded and data entered and then analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 15.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis is used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories. Friedman's comparison test is a technique is used to group the variables by comparing mean rank. It helps the researcher to identify the statements which are highly influenced the measuring variables. Steinkuehler and Williams (2006) have indicated the reasons for consumers engaging in word of mouth: Satisfied customers call word-of-mouth for many reasons, including they like to help others, for the reduction of cognitive conflict, Draw attention to them, May have reservations about what others think positive, Avoid going into the negatives. But Dissatisfied consumers call word of mouth, because: To vent about what offended, Reduce anxiety and Warn others. Extremely satisfied customers, and those who are not satisfied at all, both, have greater impact, because word of mouth by them will be more extreme. But some researchers believed that customer satisfaction does not mean engaging in positive word of mouth, but should motivate the customer to echo the positive word of mouth (Writz and Chew, 2002) have reported that, the good relationship between the customer and the organization is the most important incentive in this aspect. We can say that word of mouth is a double -edged Sword, because the organization can reap many benefits through the positive word of mouth. (Lue,

2009) has reported that "word of mouth, or the voice of the customer is one of the most effective tools for generating sales and future cash flows.

Table 1: Profile Of The Respondents

Profile	Frequency	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Age of Respondent	Less than 30 years	30	6.2
	31-40 years	97	20.0
	41-50 years	207	42.7
	51 years & above	151	31.1
Qualification	Primary	215	44.3
	Graduate	122	25.2
	PG/Professional	68	14.0
	Diploma	80	16.5
Experience	Less than 5 years	76	15.7
	5-10 years	165	34.0
	11-15 years	91	18.8
	16-20 years	153	31.5
Type of vehicles owned	LCV	281	57.9
	HCV	204	42.1
No. of LCV owned	LCV - 1	207	42.7
	LCV - 2	36	7.4
	LCV 3-5	37	7.6
	LCV more than 5	02	0.4
No. of HCV owned	HCV - 1	44	9.1
	HCV - 2	96	19.8
	HCV 3-5	48	9.9
	HCV more than 5	16	3.3
Awareness of the Brand	Less than 5 years	49	10.1
	5-10 years	137	28.2
	11-15 years	148	30.5
	16 years & above	151	31.1

Source: Primary Data - computed

With regards to experience, 34.0 percent of the respondents have the experience of 5 to 10 years followed by 31.5 percent respondents who have appreciable experience of 16 to 20 years and 18.8 percent of respondents have possessed experience of 11 to 15 years, only 15.7 percent of the respondents are observed with the experience of less than 5 years. While analysing the type of vehicle they operate, 281 respondents (57.9%) have owned Light commercial vehicles followed by 204 respondents (42.1%) that they own Heavy commercial vehicles. In respect to the number of Light commercial vehicles owned by the respondents, 207(42.7%) respondents own only one light commercial vehicle, 37 respondents (7.6%) own 3 to 5 light commercial vehicles, two commercial vehicles have been owned by 36 respondents (7.4%) and 2 respondents (0.4%) are alone found having more than 5

light commercial vehicles. Whereas in ownership of Heavy commercial vehicles, 96 respondents (19.8%) are noted be the owners of 2 heavy commercial vehicles followed by 48 respondents with 3 to 5 heavy commercial vehicles (9.9%) and a 44 respondents with (9.1%) have owned one heavy commercial vehicles. 16 respondents (3.3%) are possessing more than 5 heavy commercial vehicles. Among the respondents of the light and heavy commercial vehicles, 345 respondents (71.0%) have vehicles less than 2 years old and 140 respondents (28.9%) have owned commercial vehicles of 2 to 5 years old. The respondents purchase the replacement product from different dealers for various reasons, 247 respondents (50.9%) purchase the replacement products from more than one dealer and 238 respondents (49.1%) purchase the replacement products only from a particular dealer. When respondents are asked whether the manufacturer provide the excellent point of purchase display, 446 respondents (92.0%) replied that the manufacturer provide adequate point of purchase display, and 39 respondents (8.0%) have expressed that the manufacturer do not provide adequate point of display. Respondents are approached to say about the manufacturers' promotional supports that they provide. The analysis explains that out of 485 respondents 436 respondents (89.9%) have appreciated the promotional support that the manufacturers provides, yet 49 respondents (10.1%) says that the manufacturer do not provide adequate promotional supports. With regards to awareness of the brand at the time of replacement purchase, 151 respondents are found aware of the brand for more than 15 years, which is calculated 31.1 percent of the total respondents next to that 148 respondents are aware the brand for 10 to 15 years, it is counted 30.5 percent. Further 137 respondents are aware of the brand for 5 to 10 years, which is 28.2 percent, and only 49 respondents are aware of the brand for less than 5 years, which is at the percent of 10. When the respondents are asked the reason for buying the specific brand of tyre at the time of replacement purchase, 401 respondents have replied that the performance of the particular brand is the prime reason for

buying particular brand it is calculated to 82.7 percent of the total respondents.

Table 2: Stimulating Sources Of Information On Choosing The Replacement

Source of information	Friedman's test Mean Rank value	Chi-square	p. value	Multiple comparison test
Word of Mouth	1.11	2947.150	0.001*	1
Dealer advise	2.77			2
Sales person advise	3.38			3,4
TV advertisement	3.42			5
Print media	4.57			6
Electronic display	5.91			7
Magazines	6.96			8
Internet	7.89			

Source: Primary Data - computed (*significant at one percent level)

Communication has always been recognised to be a critical effort in purchasing consumer replacement. The researcher analysed the perception of the replacement buyer with respect to sources of information for their replacement action. Word of mouth, dealer advise, sales persons advise, TV advertisements, print media, electronic display, magazine and internet are the influencing factors considered and analysed for this study. The respondents are asked to rate their opinion towards the sources of information and displayed in this table. To know the intensity level of the respondents towards the sources of information, Friedman's test is applied. Friedman's chi-square value indicates that the statements are significantly varied by the respondents at one percent level, because p-value is 0.001. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Further Friedman's multiple comparison tests are applied to identify the most influenced sources among the respondents. Friedman's multiple comparison test results shows that eight sources are grouped into seven different categories. Among the various sources of information, word of mouth source plays the dominant role and occupy at the first position followed by Dealer's advice at the second position. The advice of sales person and Television advertisement jointly contribute and take place to the third position. Print media advertisement occupies the fourth place followed by Electronic display at the fifth place, magazine advertisement

advertisement is ranked at the sixth place and internet advertisement occupies to the seventh position. If a consumer is satisfied they will praise the product among their friends, relatives, neighbors or colleagues and they may recommend the product to people, or they may intent to buy the same product, or may buy again in near future. This result is supported by J. D. Power (2010) that while going for tyre shopping owners are relying less upon print, radio and television advertisement. Elden M. Wirtz and Kenneth E. Miller (1977) said that word of mouth or personal communication from an intermediate and trusted source is typically more influential than media communication. Post purchase communication led to a market increase in the number of recommendation of the retailer. Consumers, when considering major purchase do often consult friends and relatives for recommendation. J. D. Power (2003) found that more than 60 percent of the tyre buyers access the Internet, but only 16 percent of them use it when they need to buy tyres. Barry L. Bayus (1991) said that purchase is influenced by friends, magazine advertisement, magazine article, news paper advertisement, news paper article, radio, TV, dealer advise and dealer brochure. Mukundadas et al. (2004) explained that mainly in the age group of 15-25 years make their purchase decisions on the basis of TV advertisement. J.D. Power (2009) in this study said that the Internet is the most widely used information source among intenders. About 85 percent said that they go online for information about vehicle under consideration. Those who use the Internet for vehicle information, most often go for search on consumer reviews and reliability ratings. Other information sources used frequently are auto shows (53 percent) automotive magazines (52 percent), and television (49 percent). The study suggests that the manufacturers would be well served by utilizing the Internet for marketing, as it can be particularly effective in reaching their desired targets.

Findings

The respondent's opinion towards various sources of information significantly varied within the group. It is found that word of

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information is a prime source for providing useful information about the tyre before purchase. Dealer advice, sales persons advise, television advertisements are the sources have moderate level of influence on information about the tyres. But, the respondents are felt that print media, electronic display, magazine articles and Internet are the sources have least level impact.

Conclusion

Among the various sources of information which is influencing the customer during the

replacement time is "word of mouth". Hence, the manufacturers' gives quality product with reasonable price the customer will repeatedly buy the same brand of tyre which may lead positive information about the tyre. And if manufacturer appoint trained sales persons, they can meet the replacement customer personally and can give positive information about the product which may lead good sales to the company and satisfaction to the customer.

References

- Duncan, T and Moriarty (1997). *Driving Brand Value*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Arndt, J. (1967). Word-of-Mouth Advertising: A Review of the Literature. Advertising Research Foundation, New York.
- Richins ML (1983). Negative word-of-mouth by dis-satisfied consumers: A pilot study. *Journal of Marketing*, 47, 68-78.
- Richins ML (1987). A multivariate analysis of responses to dissatisfaction. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 15,(3), 24-31.
- Mizerski RW (1982). An attribution explanation of the disproportionate influence of unfavourable information. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 9, 301-310.
- Imran Anwar Mir(2011). Impact of the Word of Mouth on Consumers' Attitude Towards the Non-Deceptive Counterfeits. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 9 (1): 51-56.
- Norbert H. Meiners1, Ulf Schwarting and Bernd Seeberger (2010). The Renaissance of Word-of-Mouth Marketing: A 'New' Standard in Twenty-First Century Marketing Management?! *International Journal of Economic Sciences and Applied Research* 3 (2): 79-97.
- WOMMA (2008). An Introduction to Word of Mouth Marketing, <http://www.womma.org/wom101/> (accessed 4/6/2010).
- Alexander, R.S. (1964). *Marketing Definitions*. Chicago: American Marketing Association.
- Rosen, E. (2009). *The Anatomy of Buzz Revisited: Real-life Lessons in Word-of-Mouth Marketing*, New York, Doubleday Publishing Group.
- Carl, W.J.(2006). 'What's all the Buzz About? Everyday Communication and the Relational Basis of Word-of-Mouth and Buzz Marketing Practices', *Management Communication Quarterly*, 19 (4). 603-634.
- Nyilasy, G. (2005). 'Word of mouth – what we really know – and what we don't'. Kirby, J. and Marsden, P. (Eds.): *Connected Marketing: The Viral, Buzz and Word of Mouth Revolution*, Oxford, Elsevier.161-185.
- Sernovitz, A. (2007). Is viral marketing the same as word of mouth? <http://www.damniwish.com/2007/10/is-viral-market.html> (accessed 4/6/2010).
- GfK Roper Consulting. (2006). Word-of-Mouth Phenomenon Spreads Across the Globe According to Worldwide GfK Roper Consulting Study, <http://www2.prnewswire.com/cgi-bin/stories.pl?ACCT=109&STORY=/www/story/06-20-2006/0004383802&EDATE=> (accessed 4/6/2010).
- The Nielsen Company. (2009). *Trust, Value and Engagement in Advertising*, <http://de.nielsen.com/pubs/documents/NielsenTrustAdvertisingGlobalReportJuly09.pdf> (accessed 4/6/2010).
- Duncan, T. and S. Moriarty. (1997). *Driving Brand Value*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Weinberger MG & Dillon WR. (1980). The effects of unfavourable product rating information. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 7, 528-532.
- Wright P.(1974). The harassed decision maker: Time pressures, distractions, and the use of evidence. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59 (5), 555-561.
- Writz, Jochen and Chew, Patricia (2002). The Effects of Incentives Deal Satisfaction and Tie Strength on Word of Mouth Behavior. *International Journal of service*,13(2), 141
- Eldon M.Wirtz and Kenneth E.Miller. (1977). The Effect of Post-Purchase Communication on Consumer Satisfaction and on Consumer Recommendation of the Retailer. *Journal of Retailing*, 53(2).
- Power, J.D. (2010). *Asia-Pacific Japan Replacement tyre Customer satisfaction index study – report*.
- Barry L. Bayus. (1991). The Consumer Durable Replacement Buyer. *Journal of Marketing*, 55, 42-51.